

PLANKTOSCOPE-BASED TECHNOLOGY: ADDRESSING MICRO-SCALE MONITORING NEEDS IN IMTA SYSTEMS

M. Pias, B. Guterres, G. Orazi., P. Drews, V. Oliveira, S. Botelho, N. Duarte, L. Poersch, W. Wasielesky, M. Malheiros, T. Teixeira, C. Dora, P. Barros, E. Flores and E. Ravagnan*
Federal University of Rio Grande, Av. Itália – KM 8, Rio Grande (Brazil)
E-mail: guterres.brana@gmail.com

Introduction

Integrated multitrophic aquaculture (IMTA) has garnered growing interest in enhancing sustainability through the sequestration of waste and subsequent primary production. Additionally, it promotes a circular economy and boosts ecosystem services associated with lower trophic-level cultures (Sanz-Lázaro, and Sanchez-Jerez, 2020). IMTA systems encounter several challenges, including micro-level threats such as Harmful Algae Blooms (HAB) and emerging microplastic (MP) pollution. MPs have captured global attention following reports on massive trash islands within all ocean gyres, suggesting they are polluting aquatic ecosystems on an unprecedented scale (Connan et al., 2021). MPs can harm IMTA systems through various pathways, such as releasing toxic compounds and distributing potentially harmful non-native microorganisms. In addition to causing rapid oxygen depletion within aquatic environments, HABs may release toxic substances and cause serious environmental impacts in aquatic ecosystems (ZOHD and ABBASPOUR, 2019). FlowCam¹ is a well-established technology for micro-scale assessment based on flow cytometry. However, it is an expensive and bulky equipment, which makes it impractical for low-cost and large-scale applications. On the other hand, PlanktonScope² is an affordable and modular flow cytometry platform tailored for citizen oceanography. It is a versatile and economical device that can be easily adapted for many field applications. The All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project aims to define, support, and promote IMTA across the Atlantic area. The present work explores possible adaptations to the PlanktoScope technology to meet IMTA lab needs regarding micro-scale water sample assessment and its validation for HABs and MPs monitoring within a lab-based setup and a Brazilian IMTA cultivation system.

Modified PlanktoScope unity and technology validation

The proposed technology offers an economical solution by adapting the PlanktoScope unit for use in micro-scale monitoring of phytoplankton and microplastics, leveraging Artificial Intelligence (AI) within IMTA systems. Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the technology's validation in a relevant setting, specifically within a Brazilian IMTA laboratory. End-user feedback underscored the technology usefulness in meeting the specific requirements of IMTA operations.

Fig. 1 - Technology validation at a Brazilian IMTA lab system.

Conclusions

The present work presented a cost-effective solution based on the PlanktoScope open-hardware and open-software solution for addressing micro-scale microplastics and phytoplankton monitoring at IMTA farms. Technology validation and user-feedback assessment at a Brazilian IMTA lab highlighted technology usefulness for both application.

Acknowledgements

This work is part of the ASTRAL (All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture) project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 863034.

References

- CONNAN, Maëlle et al. The Indian Ocean 'garbage patch': Empirical evidence from floating macro-litter. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, v. 169, p. 112559, 2021.
- ZOHD, E.; ABBASPOUR, M. Harmful algal blooms (red tide): a review of causes, impacts and approaches to monitoring and prediction. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*, v. 16, p. 1789-1806, 2019.

¹ <https://www.fluidimaging.com/>

² <https://www.planktoscope.org/>